

WOMEN'S HEALTH IN BUKHARA: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS (1991-2000)

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the measures taken to strengthen women's health and protect motherhood and childhood in the Bukhara region at the end of the 20th century. The scientific coverage of practical work aimed at improving the health of women and children, expanding the scope of medical care, and increasing medical literacy through information and propaganda tools, initiated by the "For a Healthy Generation" Foundation, the Red Crescent Society, and other organizations, will be provided. The article shows positive developments in medical and social conditions based on statistical data.

BUXORODA XOTIN-QIZLAR SALOMATLIGI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR (1991-2000-yillar)

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Buxoro viloyati, ayollar salomatligi, sog'lom avlod, tibbiy yordam, tibbiy savodxonlik, "Ambulans Bens", jamiyat sog'ligi, onalik va bolalik, tibbiy-ijtimoiy islohotlar, Qizil Yarim Oy jamiyati.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada XX asr oxirlarida Buxoro viloyatida ayollar salomatligini mustahkamlash, onalik va bolalikni himoya qilish yo'lida amalga oshirilgan chora-tadbirlar tahlil qilinadi. "Sog'lom avlod uchun" jamg'armasi, Qizil Yarim Oy jamiyati va boshqa tashkilotlar tashabbusi bilan ayollar va bolalar salomatligini yaxshilashga qaratilgan amaliy ishlar, tibbiy yordam ko'lamining kengaytirilishi, axborot-targ'ibot vositalari orqali tibbiy savodxonlikni oshirish bo'yicha olib borilgan faoliyatlar ilmiy asosda yoritiladi. Maqolada statistik ma'lumotlar asosida tibbiy-ijtimoiy holatlarning ijobiy siljishlari ko'rsatilgan.

ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЖЕНЩИН В БУХАРЕ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ (1991-2000 гг.)

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«Скорая помощь Бенс»,
общественное здоровье,
материнство и детство,
социальные реформы,
Общество Красного Полумесяца.

ABSTRACT

В данной статье анализируются меры, предпринятые в Бухарской области в конце XX века для укрепления здоровья женщин, а также по защите материнства и детства. Освещается деятельность, направленная на улучшение здоровья женщин и детей, реализованная по инициативе Фонда «Здоровое поколение», Общества Красного Полумесяца и других организаций. В статье рассматриваются практические действия по расширению объёма медицинской помощи, повышению медицинской грамотности через информационно-пропагандистские средства, а также другие мероприятия, проведённые на научной основе. На основе статистических данных в статье отражены положительные изменения в медико-социальной сфере.

Introduction. In the second half of the 1990s, the complex socio-economic processes associated with the first years of Uzbekistan's independence required systematic measures to protect the health of the population, especially women and children, and improve the quality of medical services in the Bukhara region. During this period, a number of social projects and initiatives in the medical field were implemented in the region to improve women's health, prepare them for marriage, increase their medical literacy, and promote a healthy lifestyle. In cooperation with state and public organizations, the infrastructure of the healthcare system has been strengthened, and clubs, centers, and mobile teams have been established to expand the scope of medical and social assistance. The work carried out by the "For a Healthy Generation" Foundation was particularly noteworthy.

Analysis and results. The Bukhara Regional Women's Committee organized the "Barkamol Qizlar" and "Yosh Kelinchak" clubs.¹ The main task of the clubs was to prepare young girls in the region for marriage, create a healthy environment in the family, and train them to become home nurses who could provide first aid.

According to data provided by the regional statistics committee, in 1995 the number of children with disabilities in the region was 658, or 16.6 percent, but in 1996 it decreased to 603, or 11.8 percent. It can be seen that the number of women with disabilities increased from 1,730 in 1995, or 43.6 percent, to 2,416 in 1996, or 47.2 percent.² This negative trend indicates an increase in factors affecting women's health. In particular, diseases during pregnancy, the quality of medical care, psycho-emotional pressures, and the negative impact of the socio-economic environment on women's health may be the reason for this increase.

¹ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2028-yig'ma jild, 19-varaq.

² O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2559-yig'ma jild, 267-varaq.

These statistics indicate the need for a gender-based analysis of social, especially health, issues. At the same time, it remains urgent to develop special programs to prevent disability and strengthen the implementation of strategic tasks aimed at protecting women's health.

In order to combat the increasing number of diseases during pregnancy and increase women's medical literacy, the Bukhara regional television has launched the programs "Ziynat", "Health is the wealth of the district", "Family and life", "Ayolga mehr kerak", and radio and newspapers have launched broadcasts and articles under the headings "Iqbol", "Hakim malshalati", "Sog'lom avlod uchun", "Dugonajonlar", "Kizlar - oila saodati"³ The issue of women's health was considered as the health of the future generation and followed the path taken by international experience. This advocacy work is based on international experience and closely links women's health with the health of the future generation.

In 1995, 15 maternity hospitals and 11 postpartum rehabilitation departments operated in the region, and almost all of them underwent initial reconstruction.⁴ As a result, the necessary conditions for young mothers and children have been created. This indicates that the necessary opportunities have been created for young mothers and their children, and the infrastructure for ensuring maternal and child health has been strengthened. All these measures are considered an important part of the state policy aimed at improving women's health.

As a result of surveys conducted by the regional branch of the "For a Healthy Generation" Foundation and the health department, in 1996, information was provided that 100% of young mothers and children in all districts of the region had anemia.⁵ This situation indicates that health problems have worsened among the region's population, in particular, there is a shortage of essential micronutrients - iron, folic acid, and vitamin B12 - during pregnancy, breastfeeding, and childhood. Therefore, a comprehensive set of measures was determined to eliminate this problem. In particular, since January 1997, at the initiative of the Chairperson of the Republican Women's Committee D. Gulumova, propaganda work on the theme "Women's health is the basis of society's health" was carried out in the Gijduvan, Karakul, Olot, Shofirkon, Vobkent and Romitan districts of the region. These lectures were aimed not only at medical and educational goals, but also at arming women with knowledge about healthy eating, sanitary and hygienic requirements, and taking vitamins and iron supplements during pregnancy, thereby eliminating the root of the problem.

Another important aspect of these measures is that they were implemented with the participation of medical experts, combining theoretical information with practical advice. Since women's health is considered a public asset, it is natural that continuous support and opportunities are provided at the global and local levels to maintain and strengthen the health of girls from the day they are born.⁶ This approach also represents the formation of an effective model of cooperation between the health system and local governments. At the same

³ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2024-yig'ma jild, 149-varaq.

⁴ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2028-yig'ma jild, 20-varaq.

⁵ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2024-yig'ma jild, 150-varaq.

⁶ Ismailova F. Ayollar va bolalar salomatligini saqlash // International scientific journal science and innovation. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8372337

time, these activities are strategically important in terms of linking women's health with the stability of society as a whole and the health of future generations.

Based on the observed problems, sufficient conditions were created to improve the quality of education in the city of Bukhara, Peshku and Karakul Medical Colleges, and the Bukhara State Medical Institute, and to train young men and women who will provide quality medical services to the population of the region, and specialists from abroad were also attracted.

The issue of improving the health of mothers and women, providing them with free and quality medical services has been raised to the level of state policy. As a result of the gradual reforms, emergency medical care, "Mother and Child Screening", perinatal, reproductive health, pathological anatomy, oncology, and AIDS centers have been established in the region. In 1996-1997, in order to improve the health of the population in need of assistance, contacts were established with the Swiss Red Cross Society, and measures were taken to obtain medical equipment, bandages, and medicines.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 171 "On the organization of a medical and social patronage system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on February 22, 1996, and based on the Resolution of the regional governor No. 72 of 1996: A mobile medical and social brigade was established under the Bukhara regional branch of the "Soglom avlod uchun" foundation.⁷ An obstetrician-gynecologist, a paramedic-laboratory technician, and a sociologist were also involved in the team.

Based on this data, it can be seen that at the end of the 20th century, systemic reforms were implemented in the Bukhara region aimed at strengthening the healthcare system and increasing social protection of the population. The establishment of 15 medical and social assistance centers and 19 Red Crescent chambers in the region indicates significant infrastructural changes in this direction. These centers are important intermediaries to provide medical assistance to the population, and have become especially important in providing services to the most vulnerable groups.

In addition, the launch of adapted hospitals with 50 beds in Bukhara district and 28 beds in Jondor district has increased the availability of medical services in the coverage areas of the region and made it possible to provide primary and specialized medical care close to the population.⁸ The involvement of qualified specialists and graduates of regional medical schools in these hospitals reflects the well-staffed health care system and the attention paid to young personnel.

A special highlight is the work of the "Soglom avlod uchun" Foundation through the "Ambulance Benz" medical vehicle brigade. These mobile services have expanded the possibilities of providing medical services, especially to the population living in remote areas and remote villages of the region. According to statistics, in 1997, 2,105 patients, 3,677 mothers of fertile age and 5,002 children were provided with medical assistance through this service.⁹

⁷ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2024-yig'ma jild, 150-varaq.

⁸ O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2559-yig'ma jild, 72,73-varaq.

⁹ O'zMA, M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2559-yig'ma jild, 73-varaq.

These indicators mean that medical services aimed at the most vulnerable segments of the population - mothers and children - were prioritized. This, in turn, is a strategic approach that has served not only to improve the health of the population, but also to the healthy formation of the future generation. In short, the reforms carried out during this period are an example of a systematic and comprehensive approach aimed at improving the health system, covering all segments of the population, and improving the quality of medical care.

Conclusion. At the end of the 20th century, comprehensive programs aimed at improving the health of women and children in the Bukhara region, measures to raise a healthy generation and protect motherhood led to significant social changes. As a result of the activities of the "For a Healthy Generation" Foundation and other social organizations, significant achievements were made in the field of women's health, reproductive medicine and perinatal services. Measures that included expanding the scope of medical and social assistance, increasing medical literacy, as well as supporting motherhood and childhood, served to improve the general health of the population in the region.

References:

1. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2028-yig'ma jild, 19-varaq.
2. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2559-yig'ma jild, 267-varaq.
3. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2024-yig'ma jild, 149-150-varaqlar.
4. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2028-yig'ma jild, 20-varaq.
5. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2024-yig'ma jild, 150-varaq.
6. O'zMA. M-37 fond, 1-ro'yxat, 2559-yig'ma jild, 72-73-varaqlar.
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